

The Role of Digital Finance Innovation in Promoting Sustainable Development Goals (DInnoFin)

Version 4

Description

Project title in Latvian: Digitālo finanšu inovāciju loma ilgspējīgas attīstības mērķu veicināšanā (DInnoFin).

The aim of this research is to investigate how digitalization through the application of innovative technologies and solutions in the financial sector leads to the financial sector sustainable development in general and the reduction of CO2 emissions in particular as well as how Digital Technologies contribute to the achievement of sustainable development goals.

As a result of the study, it is expected to develop a conceptual framework that would describe the impact of both the technology solution (chosen by financial services companies) and the impact of processes and products based on digital and IC technology innovation including AI on SDG value chains in which financial service providers operate or are able to evaluate individual financial services process or product, business models for the achievement of SDGs. This project is intended to focus specifically on SDGs applicable to the achievement of climate neutrality goals, respectively, by classifying the impact of 'green digital finance' on the achievement of climate neutrality goals.

In developing the conceptual framework, the research team will consider the possibility of creating a system correlation framework based on data and expert opinions, structured on principles, which in turn are based on the assessment of the impact on CO2 emission in three dimensions: the underlying financial technology direct impact on CO2 emissions (1),

impact of financial processes and product solutions of digital and communication technologies on CO2 emissions in value chains (2), degree of intention to influence CO2 emissions taking into account the effectiveness of this influence (3).

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "The Role of Digital Finance Innovation in Promoting Sustainable Development Goals (DInnoFin).", No. BA-PA-2024/1-0031

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

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Organizations

BA School of Business and Finance, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: The Role of Digital Finance Innovation in Promoting Sustainable Development Goals (DInnoFin)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Project: "The Role of Digital Finance Innovation in Promoting Sustainable Development Goals (DInnoFin)" Nr. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0031

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Semi-structured interviews

Semi-structure interview data on how collaboration of FinTech companies, financial institutions, governments and environmental organizations can contribute to the creation of a holistic ecosystem that supports green digital finance

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Purpose is to assess criteria on how collaboration of FinTech companies, financial institutions, governments and environmental organizations can contribute to the creation of a holistic ecosystem that supports green digital finance.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Other

Semi-structured interviews

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

25

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

As of now research group has not identified industry representative data on research topic that could be used in the research.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any available PDF reader.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-02-28

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Anonymization.

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Methodological materials

Created methodological materials on research topic that can be used for updates of existing teaching materials in various study courses. The project team will create a project website and a MOODLE platform with learning resources using a science-based approach and plan to maintain it after the end of the project as well.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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3 Resources and Security

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